

APPLICATION OF LANGUAGE SKILLS IN LESSON HOUR

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Abstract:

Now a days teaching and learning are most of the essential, basic and integral part of the education for educators as well as pupils. Teacher and student both have the equal weightage in the education. Learning process puts both teacher and student in front of each other. Today importance is given to the self-study. It means today's education takes extra-ordinary efforts to make learner independent learner. As we know communication is most important part of teaching learning process. Ability to communicate effectively and clear, brief manner is a skill we need to master. To help the teaching and learning process, teacher find effective ways to create communication activities, provide and recommends source material for students in teaching hour. So we can say teacher not only play the role of teacher but also role of instructor, supervisor. In a teaching hour teacher suggests and provides audio visual aids, electronics and also recommends students various form of information technology. Active and creative learner increase their competence in all the skill. The motivation behind this point is to know the significance of use of all abilities within an exercise hour. The teacher is allowed to utilize variety of techniques and methodologies to make them competence in linguistic interaction. And to use all the skill effectively.

Keywords: Skills, Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing.

Objectives:

Objectives of the present study are:

- 1) To identify the role of teacher in teaching learning process.
- 2) To develop the listening, speaking, reading, and writing skill for expressing thoughts effectively.
- 3) To create an awareness about all strategies, techniques, and technology use in language learning.

Review of literature:

1. **G. H. Suryawanshi (2008):** explained in his book about the various skills in the regard of teaching and learning process. Further, he explained the teaching methodologies for English teaching. He also explain the methods and techniques for teaching-learning of the four linguistic skills that is listening, speaking, reading and writing in detail.
2. **Curriculum development cell, MSBTE, Mumbai (2012):** explain in detail the curriculum goals with the desired skills, which includes life skills, technical skills, intellectual skills and motor skills.

3. **Lorena Manaj Sadiku (2015):** described the importance of four skills in her research paper. Four skills activities in the language is one of the most valuable things. It can be change the listening scenario through listening, speaking, reading and writing. These four skills develop the ability to express into words through speaking or writing.

Introduction:

The role of language in communication is very important. The absence of language is mere dearth of communication. To achieve mastery of a language learner need to be competent in four skills i.e. listening, speaking, reading and writing skill. These four refer skills also known as language skills and these four essential skills of language interrelated with each other because we generally use more than one skill at a time. A skill is a tact, expertness and dexterity. It is a practice ability. It implies facility, ease smoothness and accuracy in and doing or to do something. These four language skills are abilities and tacts. They are essential skills for learning any language and using the language for various purposes. These skills develop accuracy, and ease and ability in using the language. Now it is duty of teacher how to apply these skills in lesson hour to make student familiar with all these skills. There is specific sequence of learning skills and acquainted with any language. LSRW is the correct order of teaching the skills according to Robert Lado (1957). It can be shown as follow.

English is universal as well as official language in the most of countries. Many people communicate in English language and this language becomes language of media, technology, tourism, international technology, politics, etc. English in many countries teaches as a second and foreign language. To learn English language it become necessary to know all these skills.

These four fundamental skills can be divided into two parts.

1. Productive skills (active skills)- speaking, writing
2. Receptive skills (passive skills)-listening, reading

Speaking and writing these skills are called as productive skills because while using these two skills a learner or user is not only active but also produces sounds in speaking and in writing it produces symbols such as letters pictures etc. On the other hand, listening and reading these two skills are considered receptive skills because here a learner is generally passive and obtains information either through listening or reading skill. As the four skills are interrelated, the active skills depend on passive skills for their fluency and development.

Listening skill:

It is first and most significant part of communication and learning a language. It is the skill in which proper habits are formed to receive auditory signals, and to understand them logically. It consists in acquiring used to English sounds, words, phrases and sentences. It requires recall of content through associations between the English content and expressions. The auditory understanding possible only when careful attention is paid to what is heard. It requires adequate memory span.

In order to develop listening skill of the students, they should have plenty of opportunities to listen to the English sounds, phrases, and sentence. Therefore teacher needs to talk in the English language. If possible, he can use audio aids to provide listening practice. The most important activity is to provide auditory signals to the students. Understanding of spoken utterance is more important, so for teacher it is important to speak and introduce the utterances in proper contexts. The easiest way is to create association bonds between the utterance and some aids that will help understanding. There are some efforts that teachers can do. They can provide students intensive listening class that can beat all challenges in listening activities. As we technology plays very essential role in learning procedure so at college level teacher can show them film and video clip which base on conversation skill. From audiobooks to apps, there is a multitude of technological resources, active listening also means listening to understand rather than reply. Reinforce building good listening skill by encouraging students to practice asking clarifying questions to fully understand the speaker's intended message.

Speaking skill:

It is the skill to providing meaningful and appropriate verbal signals. In order to speak, proper content is selected, content and expression are combined for constructing sentences, and the sentences are supported by proper intonation and stress patterns. This skill needs great facility to use the language, an adequate memory span to complete sentences and to ensure proper sequences of sentences.

Teaching of speaking skill to student's means, to teach our learners to produce English sounds and sound patterns, use word and sentence stress, intonation pattern and rhythm of the that particular language, and select appropriate words sentences according to the proper social setting audience, situation and subject matter.

Now many linguistics and ESL teachers approve on that students learn to speak in the second language by "interacting". Communicative language teaching and collaborative learning serve best for this aim. Communicative language teaching is based on real-life situations that require communication. By

using this method in ESL classes, students will have the opportunity of communicating with each other in the target language. In brief, ESL teachers should create a classroom environment where students have real-life communication, authentic activities, and meaningful tasks that promote oral language. This can occur when students collaborate in groups to achieve a goal or to complete a task. For that teacher promotes some activities like, role play, debate, group discussion, dialogue speaking, introducing themselves, brainstorming, storytelling, interviews, story completions, picture describing etc.

In lesson hour teacher can be used various technology like,

1. Communication lab
2. Speech recognition software
3. TELL
4. Internet
5. Pod casting
6. Quick Link Pen
7. Quicktionary

Reading skill:

It is the skill of grasping the English language through its written symbols. It consists of recognition of letters, words, phrases and sentences. It requires proper grouping of letters of words, and words of sentences. Reading without understanding is not useful. Therefore, intelligent reading is a must.

There are some techniques of reading text material to concentrate on some specific procedure for reading. These techniques are known as:

1. Skimming
2. Scanning
3. Glossing
4. Questioning
5. Mapping
6. SQ3R technique.

To improve reading skill teacher should suggest students to use these reading techniques.

Skimming: it is the technique of reading to get the ‘cream’ or gist of the text.

Scanning: Scanning is used to search specific information from a reference book.

Glossing: it is writing in margins of the text brief comments, cross-references, explanations, observations etc.

Questioning: this means writing questions in the margins while reading. These questions might simply indicate what the text tries to answer.

Mapping: this is a technique of representing graphically the concepts and prepositions

Writing skill:

It can be defined as the skill of putting down the conventional symbols used in the English

discussed in the text. Language for expressing thoughts, feelings, desires etc. this skill incorporate penmanship, i.e. simple handwriting, and written composition of various types. Writing skill demands adequate awareness. About specific styles and registers for varieties of subjects. A friendly letter can begin with ‘Dear Amol, I am writing from the steps of the Taj’ but a formal business letter cannot. Proper vocabulary selection is necessary. There are fixed formulas and conventions that should be followed in writing. Teacher have to use following techniques while teaching in a class, Story Writing, Dialogue construction/writing Making Paragraph, essay writing, Bio-sketch writing, Note-making, Email Writing, Diary Writing, Article Writing (General and Technical, Writing the answers of questions given in the picture on the basis of family photo, Free Writing, letter writing, report writing, Business (Inquiry) Letter, Developing English Sentences through Drill Method Teachers can use the drill method to teach sentences of English where students have freedom to make sentence with the help of words given.

Integration of four skills:

Two activities that make use of all four skills in tandem are Self-introduction and Reading and Retell. Self-introduction takes the answers to a series of personal questions (name, age, grade level, where you live, members of your family, favorite sports, animals, colors, subjects, etc.) and sequences them into a self introduction. Students are given large visuals to generate each component of the self-introduction. The teacher can point to each picture while modeling a self-introduction (students are *listening*) and then invite learners to introduce themselves (*speaking*) to one or two of their peers. Some of the visuals can then be changed and the students can be invited to introduce themselves to others in the class to whom they have never spoken. This activity can be adapted to become a regular (daily, weekly) warm-up activity to get learners talking in the target language. Having covered *listening* and *speaking* in the oral self-introduction, a scenario can then be created in which learners must *write* a self-introduction to a potential home stay host. The same picture cues can be used, reconfigured to show a salutation, closing and signature. The picture cues provide learners with support without giving them a text to memorize. In multilevel SL classes, graded readers can be excellent springboards for another activity that integrates the four skills- a reading and retell. First, learners select a book or story at their own level and *read* it. Learners are then given a template to follow to summarize their thoughts about the story (*writing*). The summary is designed to help learners gauge the amount of detail required in a retell. After additional practice *reading* the summary silently and aloud several times, learners are asked to select two or three illustrations from the book to help them tell the story. They then practice telling the story by using the pictures and remembering what they wrote in the template. Students find a partner who has not read the same story and retell (*speaking*) their story to one another using the selected illustrations. Partners not only listen to the retell but also complete a feedback checklist (*writing*) about the retell. After *reading* the feedback, partners switch roles.

Purpose of four skills activities:

Four skills activities in the language classroom serve many valuable purposes: they give learners

support, opportunities to create, contexts in which to use the language for exchanges of real information, evidence of their own ability (proof of learning), it increase competence of using language and most important, it increase confidence of learner. Reading is fun-way to knowledge hunt. We read or see innumerable quotes and proverbs on reading. How far is it true? It is true indeed- reading brings wisdom. Through reading, we learn a lot and it is the most prominent language skill. But the fact of making a reading habit or being good at it is the question here. For now, students, adults and even educators read very less. It is a well-known fact that when there were no televisions or computers or other forms of entertainment, reading was a primary leisure activity among the educated lot. People would spend hours reading books and travel to lands far away or enjoy love, cherish victorious moments and live history-in their minds. The tragedy is that, with time, people have lost their skill and passion to read. Reading has declined among every group of people in today's world of technology and entertainment. There are many other exciting and thrilling options available, aside from books. And that is a shame because reading offers a productive approach to improving language- vocabulary and word power for example. When you possess rich vocabulary, you listen better as you understand more; then you can write better with more words to choose from; obviously you can speak better because of your intense word power. It is advisable to indulge in at least half an hour of reading a day to keep abreast of the various styles of writing and new vocabulary. Thus, the need to develop a habit to read is very important. Well, the skills will hopefully jump in automatically once the strong genuine habit has been established. The best and easiest approach is however, to make a small effort to read a piece a day... you will surely succeed.

Conclusion:

Four skills activities in the language classroom serve many cherished tenacities. It gives support to learners with the opportunities to create, contexts in which to use the language for exchanges of real information, evidence of their own ability (proof of learning), it increase ability of using language and most important, it increase confidence of learner. With the help of these four skills, the learners can be assured of having good communication skill, which great necessity in today's competitive world. By the guidance of tutor, learner will develop their skills and able to use language for expressing their thought emotion, and ideas effectively. They also use technology for development of communication skill and by that to develop personality. So the role of teacher in language class is to produce conditions and develop activities so that students are able to practice the language in a meaningful context.

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